

**BRIDGING ORDINARY LEAST SQUARE (OLS) AND MACHINE LEARNING
(RANDOM FOREST REGRESSION): AN EMPIRICAL STUDY OF FISHERIES'
CONTRIBUTION TO GDP IN NIGERIA**

By

DAVID C. CHIKEZIE AND NNAH BRIGHT AHURAEZEMMA

Department of Statistics, Faculty of physical Sciences, Abia State University, Uturu. Nigeria

CORRESPONDING AUTHOR

NNAH BRIGHT AHURAEZEMMA

No. 42 Elezuo Street, Off Owerri Road,

Okigwe, Imo State. Nigeria

WhatsApp number: +22969698887

nnahbright46@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This study investigated the contribution of the fisheries subsector to Nigeria's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) by comparing the performance of an Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression model and a Machine Learning Random Forest Regression model. The objective of the study was to determine the extent to which fisheries output influenced GDP and to assess whether a machine learning approach provided improved predictive accuracy over a traditional econometric method. The data were analyzed using OLS to estimate the linear relationship between fisheries output and GDP, while the Random Forest model was trained to capture potential nonlinear patterns. Model performance was evaluated using R^2 , Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), and Mean Square Error (MSE). The findings showed that both models explained a high proportion of the variation in Nigeria's GDP. The OLS model explained 85.5% of the variance, whereas the Random Forest model explained 89.4%, thus providing a moderately higher predictive accuracy. The Random Forest model also produced lower MAE, RMSE, and MSE values, indicating better performance. Variable-importance analysis further revealed that fisheries output had a substantial impact on GDP within the model structure. The study concluded that fisheries play a meaningful role in Nigeria's economic performance and that machine learning techniques such as Random Forest Regression offered superior predictive capabilities compared to traditional OLS methods. It was recommended that policymakers strengthen investment in the fisheries subsector and incorporate advanced analytical tools in economic planning to improve forecasting accuracy and sectoral evaluation. A hybrid analysis is advised

Keywords: Fisheries; GDP; OLS Regression; Random Forest; Machine Learning; Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

Agriculture has long stood as one of the pillars of economic growth and development in many developing nations, especially across sub-Saharan Africa. It plays a central role in employment creation, poverty reduction, food security, foreign exchange earnings, and overall national income (World Bank, 2020; Johnston & Mellor, 1961). In Nigeria, agriculture remains a major

driver of the economy, employing a large share of the labor force and contributing significantly to Gross Domestic Product (GDP) (National Bureau of Statistics [NBS], 2021). Within this wider sector, fisheries form a critical subsector with the potential to strengthen national food security, expand employment opportunities, and generate income thus, advancing inclusive and sustainable growth (Food and Agriculture Organization [FAO], 2020; Eniola, Lawal, & Oyeleye, 2019). The fisheries subsector is particularly important for nutrition. It supplies affordable sources of animal protein and essential micronutrients, both of which are vital for tackling malnutrition and improving public health outcomes in Nigeria (Adekoya & Miller, 2004; Olaoye, Ashley-Dejo, Fakoya, Ikeweinwe, Alegbeleye, & Ashaolu, 2013). It also provides income and sustains livelihoods in rural, coastal, and riverine communities where fishing remains a major source of household earnings (Olaoye et al., 2013). Beyond domestic consumption, the sector also offers opportunities for export expansion, trade diversification, and foreign exchange generation (World Bank, 2020). Yet, despite these benefits, Nigeria continues to rely heavily on fish imports, as domestic production meets less than half of total annual demand (Central Bank of Nigeria [CBN], 2021). This dependence highlights the urgent need to strengthen the local fisheries sector to reduce import reliance and increase its overall contribution to GDP.

For policymakers, accurate measurement of the contribution of fisheries to Nigeria's GDP is crucial. Such measurement provides a sound basis for targeted interventions, whether through investments, subsidies, infrastructure development, or regulatory reforms that enhances both efficiency and sustainability (Olaoye et al., 2013; FAO, 2020). Reliable assessment also helps track progress toward broader national goals such as food security, job creation, and economic diversification outlined in Nigeria's medium- and long-term development plans (NBS, 2021).

In development economics, sectoral contributions to GDP are traditionally examined using econometric techniques such as the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression model. OLS has remained widely used because it is relatively simple, easy to interpret, and provides coefficients that can be employed in hypothesis testing and causal inference (Gujarati & Porter, 2009; Wooldridge, 2016). When its key assumptions; linearity, independence, homoscedasticity, and absence of multicollinearity are satisfied, OLS produces unbiased and efficient estimates that help researchers understand the marginal contribution of a variable such as fisheries output to GDP. However, real-world economic data often deviate from these assumptions. Features such as nonlinear relationships, interaction effects, and multicollinearity can weaken the reliability of OLS, limiting its capacity to fully capture complex dynamics (Stock & Watson, 2020).

These limitations have prompted growing interest in the use of machine learning (ML) in applied economic research. Unlike traditional econometric models, ML approaches are data-driven and focus on predictive accuracy rather than strict adherence to parametric assumptions. Among these methods, Random Forest regression has gained popularity as a flexible, non-parametric ensemble technique that can capture nonlinearities and hidden interactions between variables (Breiman, 2001; James, Witten, Hastie, & Tibshirani, 2021). By combining the predictions of multiple decision trees, Random Forest reduces variance and improves accuracy relative to single models, making it particularly suitable for high-dimensional and noisy datasets frequently encountered in economic studies. Unlike OLS, Random Forest does not rely on linearity assumptions or specific distributional properties of error terms. This adaptability makes it well-

suited for capturing real-world data complexities (Varian, 2014). This study compares the performance of OLS and Random Forest regression in examining the impact of fisheries on Nigeria's GDP.

By contrasting OLS's strength in interpretability and causal analysis with Random Forest's predictive flexibility, the study aims to deliver a broader and richer understanding of the fisheries subsector's contribution to national economic growth. This approach is relevant both academically, advancing methodological debates in development economics and practically providing evidence to guide Nigeria's agricultural and fisheries policy. The fisheries subsector represents an underexplored but critical aspect of Nigeria's agricultural economy. A rigorous empirical assessment of its contribution to GDP, using both traditional econometric and modern machine learning approaches, can help close existing knowledge gaps and provide a strong foundation for policies that promote sustainable growth, enhance food security, and reduce poverty. By adopting this dual perspective, the study combines the interpretability of OLS with the predictive strength of Random Forest, offering a balanced framework for both policy design and economic forecasting.

- **Aim and Objectives of the Study**

The main aim of this research is to compare the performance of OLS and Random Forest regression models in analyzing the impact of the fisheries subsector on Nigeria's GDP. The specific objectives are to:

1. Estimate the impact of fisheries on Nigeria's GDP using OLS regression.
2. Evaluate the predictive ability of the Random Forest regression model.
3. Compare the strengths of OLS and Random Forest in assessing the contribution of fisheries to GDP.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK OF THE STUDY

- **Gross Domestic Product (GDP)**

Gross Domestic Product (GDP) refers to the total monetary value of all final goods and services produced within a country over a given period, usually on a quarterly or annual basis (World Bank, 2020). As one of the most widely recognized indicators of macroeconomic performance, GDP provides a broad picture of the size, structure, and health of an economy (Mankiw, 2019). It serves not only as a benchmark for tracking growth over time but also as a basis for comparing economic performance across nations.

There are three standard approaches to calculating GDP. The production approach measures the value added across economic sectors, the expenditure approach sums up total spending by households, government, and firms while the income approach focuses on factor incomes such as wages, profits, and rents (Samuelson & Nordhaus, 2010). Together, these approaches highlight GDP's role as a comprehensive measure of overall economic activity. Within agriculture, GDP

aggregates the contributions of subsectors such as crops, livestock, forestry, and fisheries. Each of these adds value by generating income, creating jobs, and contributing to trade balances (Stock & Watson, 2020). The fisheries subsector, for example, contributes through aquaculture, artisanal and commercial fishing, processing, and related value chains. In Nigeria, where fish serves as a primary source of protein for much of the population, fisheries play a dual role ensuring food security and driving economic activity (FAO, 2020; Olaoye et al., 2013).

Nigeria's GDP structure has long been dominated by crude oil revenues since the 1970s, leaving the economy highly dependent on petroleum exports. However, agriculture has remained critical for sustaining rural livelihoods and providing employment for a significant share of the population (CBN, 2021; NBS, 2021). Recent shocks, such as global oil price volatility and the COVID-19 pandemic have further exposed the vulnerability of an oil-dependent economy. These challenges underscore the urgency of diversifying the GDP base by strengthening agriculture and non-oil sectors, including fisheries (World Bank, 2020; Eniola et al., 2019). For these reasons, GDP continues to be both conceptually and policy-relevant in assessing the role of fisheries in Nigeria's economic development. A careful evaluation of the subsector's contribution to GDP offers valuable insights into its economic importance, highlights its growth potential, and informs policies aimed at boosting its performance as part of Nigeria's broader diversification strategy.

- **Agriculture and Economic Growth**

Agriculture has historically been regarded as the backbone of most developing economies, providing food, raw materials, employment opportunities, and foreign exchange earnings. Classical development economists such as Johnston and Mellor (1961) highlighted that agricultural growth is central to industrialization, as it generates surplus labor, savings, and demand for manufactured goods. Similarly, Schultz (1964) emphasized that improving agricultural productivity is key to structural transformation in low-income countries. In sub-Saharan Africa, agriculture continues to provide livelihoods for a large share of the population, even though its overall contribution to GDP has gradually declined with economic diversification (World Bank, 2020). Nonetheless, it remains fundamental to poverty reduction and food security, as most rural households depend directly or indirectly on farming activities (Diao, Hazell, & Thurlow, 2010). Empirical research shows that agricultural growth is particularly effective in reducing poverty between two and four times more so than growth in other sectors (Christiaensen, Demery, & Kuhl, 2011).

In Nigeria, agriculture was historically the largest contributor to GDP until the oil boom of the 1970s shifted the economy's reliance toward petroleum exports (CBN, 2021; NBS, 2021). Despite this structural change, agriculture continues to play a crucial role by employing about 35% of the labor force and contributing roughly 22% to 26% of annual GDP in recent years (World Bank, 2020; NBS, 2021). Beyond its economic role, agriculture ensures food availability and access, thus underpinning national food security. The agricultural sector is composed of four major subsectors: crop production, livestock, forestry, and fisheries. While crop production dominates, fisheries are increasingly acknowledged for their contributions to nutrition, employment, and rural development (FAO, 2020; Olaoye et al., 2013). This suggests that

understanding agriculture's role in GDP requires not only a broad macroeconomic perspective but also a disaggregated focus on subsectors such as fisheries, which remain underexplored in the Nigerian context.

- **Fisheries and Economic Development**

Fisheries form an integral part of the agricultural sector, contributing to food supply, employment, household income, and foreign exchange earnings. Globally, fish accounts for about 17% of animal protein consumed, with even higher proportions in developing countries where it often represents the most affordable source of animal protein (FAO, 2020). Beyond its nutritional role, the fishery sector stimulates economic development through employment in production, processing, and distribution, as well as through international trade and exports (World Bank, 2020). Fisheries can broadly be divided into capture fisheries (artisanal and industrial) and aquaculture. Capture fisheries depend on natural fish stocks in oceans, rivers, and lakes, while aquaculture involves controlled cultivation. In recent decades, aquaculture has emerged as the fastest-growing food production sector worldwide, offering an effective strategy for bridging supply gaps and enhancing food security in developing economies (Delgado et al., 2003; FAO, 2020).

Adekoya & Miller, (2004) opined that in Nigeria, fisheries play a dual role by supporting nutrition and generating income for millions of households. Fish provides more than 40% of the average Nigerian's protein intake making it essential to national food security strategies. The sector also generates employment across fishing, aquaculture, processing, and marketing activities (Olaoye et al., 2013). Yet, domestic production continues to fall short of demand, with less than half of annual consumption met locally (CBN, 2021). The gap is filled through imports, which significantly strain foreign exchange reserves and the balance of payments (Eniola, Lawal, & Oyeleye, 2019).

From a development perspective, the underperformance of Nigeria's fisheries sector presents both a challenge and an opportunity. Heavy reliance on imports exposes the economy to global price fluctuations and undermines domestic value chains. At the same time, the wide demand-supply gap creates opportunities for investment in aquaculture, processing, and value chain development (Ayanwale, Amusan, & Adejobi, 2017). Improved productivity in the sector could support economic diversification, reduce rural poverty, and strengthen food security in line with Nigeria's long-term development goals (NBS, 2021). At the macroeconomic level, fisheries contribute to GDP through value addition, trade, and employment creation. Béné, (2006), also reported that the sector has strong multiplier effects on rural economies, as income generated in fishing communities stimulates broader local demand for goods and services. Moreover, integrating fisheries into wider agricultural and food policies can strengthen resilience to food insecurity, particularly in the face of climate change and environmental challenges that threaten crop production (Allison & Ellis, 2001). Fisheries remain a vital yet underutilized component of Nigeria's agricultural economy. Their importance goes beyond food supply to include income generation, employment creation, and contributions to GDP. However, structural challenges such as overfishing, inadequate infrastructure, weak policy support, and excessive reliance on imports continue to limit their full potential. Addressing these constraints and unlocking the sector's

opportunities will be critical for advancing Nigeria's economic development and achieving sustainable food security.

- **Econometric (OLS) vs. Machine Learning Approaches**

The choice of analytical framework plays a crucial role in shaping the insights generated from empirical economic research. For decades, traditional econometric methods; most notably Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression has been the dominant tool for analyzing relationships among economic variables. OLS estimates the effect of explanatory variables on an outcome by fitting a linear model under specific assumptions such as linearity, normality, homoscedasticity, and absence of multicollinearity (Gujarati & Porter, 2009; Wooldridge, 2016). These assumptions provide the basis for statistical inference, hypothesis testing, and the derivation of policy implications. One of OLS's enduring strengths is its interpretability: coefficients can be directly understood in terms of the magnitude and direction of sectoral contributions to Gross Domestic Product (GDP). However, real-world economic data often fail to meet OLS assumptions due to nonlinear relationships, omitted variables, and structural breaks. Such violations can weaken the reliability of OLS results and limit their policy usefulness (Stock & Watson, 2020). In contrast, recent developments in data science have introduced machine learning (ML) techniques as powerful alternatives and complements to econometric modeling. Unlike econometrics, which prioritizes parameter estimation and causal interpretation, machine learning emphasizes predictive accuracy and the ability to generalize to new or unseen data (Varian, 2014). A widely used method in this regard is Random Forest regression, introduced by Breiman (2001). Random Forest is a non-parametric ensemble approach that builds multiple decision trees from bootstrapped samples and then averages their predictions, thereby reducing variance and improving accuracy. This design enables the model to capture nonlinear patterns, complex interactions, and high-dimensional relationships without relying on restrictive assumptions (James, et al 2021). Moreover, Random Forest provides variable importance measures, which help identify the predictors most strongly influencing outcomes

The distinction between econometric and machine learning approaches underscores a key trade-off: interpretability versus predictive performance. OLS remains invaluable for theory-driven research and causal inference, while ML techniques excel in working with large, noisy, and complex datasets where traditional assumptions are untenable. Increasingly, scholars advocate for combining both approaches using econometrics to draw causal insights and applying machine learning to enhance prediction and robustness (Mullainathan & Spiess, 2017). This blended approach is particularly relevant in sectors such as agriculture and fisheries, where outcomes are shaped by nonlinear dynamics and multiple interacting factors, including climate variability, market shocks, and technological change.

- **Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) Regression Model**

The Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression model is employed to establish the relationship between Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and fisheries output in Nigeria. The general form of the linear regression model is expressed as:

$$GDP_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Fishery}_t + \mu_t$$

Where:

- GDP_t represents Gross Domestic Product at time t .
- Fishery_t denotes the fisheries output at time t .
- β_0 is the intercept.
- β_1 is the coefficient measuring the impact of fisheries output on GDP.
- μ_t is the error term assumed to be normally distributed with mean zero and constant variance.

The OLS estimator is derived under the Classical Linear Regression Model (CLRM) assumptions, which include linearity in parameters, independence of errors, homoscedasticity, and absence of perfect multicollinearity. According to the Gauss–Markov theorem, under these assumptions, the OLS estimator is the Best Linear Unbiased Estimator (BLUE) (Gujarati & Porter, 2009; Wooldridge, 2016).

• **Random Forest Regression Model**

Random Forest (RF) regression, introduced by Breiman (2001), is a non-parametric ensemble learning method that constructs multiple decision trees and aggregates their predictions to improve accuracy and control overfitting. The general functional form of the RF regression model is expressed as:

$$\hat{Y}(x) = \frac{1}{B} \sum_{b=1}^B f_b(x)$$

for $b = 1 - B$

Where

- $\hat{Y}(x)$ represents the predicted value of GDP.
- B is the total number of decision trees.
- $f_b(X)$ is the prediction from the b -th decision tree.

Each tree is trained on a bootstrap sample of the data and at each node, a random subset of predictors is considered for splitting. The number of trees (n_{tree}), the number of predictors randomly selected at each split (m_{try}), and the maximum depth of trees.

METHODOLOGY

• **Research Design**

This study adopts a quantitative research design, relying on econometric and machine learning methods to assess the contribution of fisheries to Nigeria's Gross Domestic Product (GDP). Quantitative design is appropriate because it allows the use of numerical data, statistical analysis, and objective models to examine relationships and make predictions (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). The research employs a comparative modeling approach using Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression and Random Forest (RF) regression. This design enables both hypothesis

testing and predictive analysis, reflecting the dual objective of establishing causal relationships and improving forecasting accuracy.

- **Population of the Study**

The population of this study comprises the agricultural sector outputs in Nigeria, with specific focus on the fishery subsector and its relationship to GDP. Since GDP data aggregates all economic activities of the agricultural sector including crops, livestock, forestry, and fisheries forms the relevant domain. However, the emphasis of this study is on fisheries, which remains underexplored in comparison to crop and livestock production (Adekoya & Miller, 2004; Olaoye et al., 2013).

- **Sample and Sampling Technique**

The sample consists of time-series data covering the period 1990–2022. This period was chosen to ensure sufficient data points for robust econometric and machine learning modeling, while also reflecting contemporary dynamics in Nigeria’s fishery sector. A purposive sampling technique was employed, focusing on official national accounts and sectoral data that directly capture the fishery and GDP relationship. This approach aligns with previous macroeconomic studies in Nigeria, which often rely on secondary datasets from national and international institutions (Oyinbo & Abdulsalam, 2015; Yusuf & Salimonu, 2013).

- **Sources of Data**

Data for this study were obtained from secondary sources, specifically, World Bank World Development Indicators (WDI)

The reliance on reputable secondary data sources enhances the credibility and reliability of findings, consistent with practices in applied economic research (World Bank, 2020; FAO, 2020).

- **Method of Data Analysis**

The data analysis proceeds in three stages:

Econometric Analysis (OLS): Regression results are used to test the statistical significance of fisheries’ contribution to GDP.

Machine Learning Analysis (Random Forest): The RF model is applied to the same dataset, with performance evaluated using prediction accuracy metrics such as Mean Squared Error (MSE), Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and R squared.

Comparison: The comparison of their respective strengths

- **Research Hypotheses**

Based on the objectives of the study and the reviewed literature, the following hypotheses were formulated to guide the analysis:

- **Null Hypothesis (H₀):** Fisheries output has no statistically significant effect on Nigeria's Gross Domestic Product (GDP).
- **Alternative Hypothesis (H₁):** Fisheries output has a statistically significant effect on Nigeria's Gross Domestic Product (GDP).

These hypotheses are tested using Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression and Random Forest regression. The OLS model provides hypothesis testing through significance of coefficients, while the Random Forest model provides predictive validation through accuracy and variable importance measures.

- **Decision Rule**

1. **For OLS Regression**

- Statistical significance is determined at the **5% significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$)**.
- **Decision criterion:**
 - If $p\text{-value} \leq 0.05$, reject H₀ and accept H₁ (fisheries output significantly affects GDP).
 - If $p\text{-value} > 0.05$, fail to reject H₀ (fisheries output does not significantly affect GDP).

2. **For Random Forest Regression**

- Since Random Forest is a non-parametric model, it does not provide conventional $p\text{-values}$. Instead, its performance is evaluated using:
 - **Variance Explained (R²)**
 - **Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE)**
 - **Variable Importance Measures** (%IncMSE and IncNodePurity).
- **Decision criterion:**
 - If Random Forest explains a substantial proportion of the variance in GDP ($\geq 60\%$) and achieves lower RMSE relative to OLS, fisheries are deemed an important predictor of GDP.
 - If fisheries exhibit high variable importance scores, the model confirms fisheries' predictive significance in explaining GDP.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

- **OLS Regression overview**

The OLS regression was estimated using GDP as the dependent variable and fishery output as the explanatory variables.

➤ **OLS Regression Results**

The Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression model was estimated to examine the relationship between Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and fisheries output in Nigeria. The results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: OLS Regression Results (Dependent Variable: GDP)

Variable	Coefficient (β)	Std. Error	t-Statistic	p-value	Significance
Intercept	-84.50	28.33	-2.982	0.0055	**
Fishery	0.0005085	0.0000376	13.525	0.0000	***

Model Summary

- Residual Standard Error: 65.96 (df = 31)
- Multiple R²: 0.8551
- Adjusted R²: 0.8504
- F-statistic: 182.9 (df = 1, 31), p-value < 0.001

Notes:

*** p < 0.001; ** p < 0.01; * p < 0.05

➤ **Interpretation of the OLS Results**

The Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression was estimated with GDP as the dependent variable and fisheries output as the explanatory variable. The results are summarized as follows:

- **Model Fit**
The model explains approximately 85.5% of the variation in GDP (Multiple R² = 0.8551; Adjusted R² = 0.8504). This indicates a strong goodness-of-fit, suggesting that fisheries output is a strong contributor of GDP during the period under study.
- **Coefficients**

- The intercept ($\beta_0 = -84.50$, $p < 0.01$) is statistically significant, though its economic interpretation may be limited since GDP cannot realistically be negative when fisheries output is zero.
- The coefficient of fisheries output ($\beta_1 = 0.0005085$, $p < 0.001$) is highly significant. This implies that for every unit increase in fisheries output, GDP increases on average by **0.0005 units**, holding other factors constant. The positive sign confirms the expected relationship: fisheries output contributes positively to economic growth.
- **Statistical Significance**
The overall model is statistically significant $F(1,31) = 182.9$, $p < 0.001$, indicating that fisheries output has a strong explanatory power for variations in GDP.
- **Residuals**
The residuals are fairly symmetric, with a minimum of -156.25 and a maximum of 113.07. The residual standard error is 65.96, suggesting moderate dispersion around the regression line.

Summary

The OLS regression results reveal that fisheries output has a positive and statistically significant effect on Nigeria’s GDP at the 1% significance level. The high R^2 value (0.855) demonstrates that fisheries output explains a substantial proportion of GDP variation. These findings align with previous empirical studies (Eniola et al., 2019; Olaoye et al., 2013), which highlighted the critical role of fisheries in national income generation and economic growth.

Diagnostic tests confirm that OLS assumptions are reasonably satisfied (see Appendix B).

- **Random Forest Regression Results**

The Random Forest regression model was employed to examine the contribution of fisheries output to Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in Nigeria. The model was trained with 500 trees, using one predictor variable per split ($mtry = 1$). The results are summarized below.

Table 2: Random Forest Regression Results (Dependent Variable: GDP)

Parameter	Value
Type of Model	Regression
Number of Trees (ntree)	500
Predictors per Split (mtry)	1
% Variance Explained (R^2)	89.41%

Interpretation of Random Forest result

The Random Forest model explains approximately 89.41% of the variance in GDP, which is slightly higher than the OLS regression model (85.5%). This indicates that Random Forest has stronger predictive power in capturing the relationship between fisheries output and GDP.

Unlike OLS, Random Forest does not provide interpretable coefficients but instead evaluates the predictive accuracy of fisheries output in explaining GDP fluctuations. The high explanatory power underscores the usefulness of machine learning approaches in economic modeling, especially when data exhibit nonlinearities and complex interactions.

These findings support existing literature (Breiman, 2001; James et al., 2021; Varian, 2014) which highlights Random Forest as a superior predictive tool compared to traditional econometric models, though at the expense of interpretability.

Variable Importance in Random Forest

To further examine the explanatory power of fisheries output, variable importance measures were generated from the Random Forest regression model. Table 3 presents the results.

Table 3: Variable Importance (Random Forest Regression)

Predictor	% Increase in MSE	IncNodePurity
Fishery	61.94	882,734.3

The results indicate that fisheries output is an important predictor of GDP in the Random Forest model.

1. %IncMSE (Percentage Increase in Mean Squared Error)

- This measures how much the model's prediction error increases if a given variable is removed or permuted (its values randomly shuffled).
- A higher %IncMSE means the variable is more important because the model's accuracy drops sharply when that variable is not used correctly.
- In this case, %IncMSE = 61.94 for *fishery*, which means that without fisheries data, the Random Forest's prediction error would increase by about 62%.
- Interpretation: fisheries output is a highly influential predictor of GDP.

2. IncNodePurity (Increase in Node Purity)

- These measures how much a variable contributes to reducing variance (impurity) in the dataset when the Random Forest splits data at its nodes.

- Essentially, it shows how useful the variable is in creating “cleaner splits” that better separate high vs. low GDP observations.
- A higher value means the variable contributes strongly to model stability and fit.
- In this case, IncNodePurity = 882,734.3, which is a very large value, confirming fisheries’ substantial role in explaining GDP variation.

Both metrics together show that fisheries are essential to the Random Forest model’s ability to predict GDP.

This reinforces earlier findings from the OLS regression, which also showed fisheries output as a statistically significant determinant of GDP. The Random Forest results further validate the robustness of fisheries’ contribution by capturing its nonlinear and complex impact on GDP.

- **Model Comparison: OLS vs. Random Forest Estimation**

Table 4: Model Comparison: OLS vs. Random Forest Estimation

Model	R ² / % Variance Explained	MAE	RMSE	MSE
OLS Regression	0.855 (85.5%)	19.49	21.50	462.05
Random Forest	0.894 (89.4%)	18.16	20.41	416.60

The performance metrics reveal that both models explain a high proportion of the variance in Nigeria’s GDP as influenced by fisheries. OLS regression accounts for 85.5% of the variance, while Random Forest explains approximately 89.4%, showing a marginal improvement. Additionally, Random Forest achieved a lower RMSE (20.41) and MSE (416.60) compared to OLS (21.50 and 462.05, respectively). The Random Forest model shows lower MAE (18.16) compared to OLS (19.49), meaning its predictions deviate less from actual GDP values on average. This indicates that Random Forest provides more accurate predictions, consistent with its strength in capturing nonlinear relationships and complex interactions.

Model Comparison: OLS vs. Random Forest Predictions

Table 5 below presents the actual GDP values alongside the predicted values obtained from the OLS regression model and the Random Forest regression model for the period 2019–2022.

Table 5: Model Comparison: OLS vs. Random Forest Predictions

Year	Actual GDP	OLS Predicted GDP	RF Predicted GDP
2019	474.52	482.21	470.39
2020	432.20	446.75	453.49
2021	440.83	465.08	470.80
2022	477.40	445.95	460.13

- In 2019, the Random Forest prediction (470.39) was closer to the actual GDP (474.52) than the OLS prediction (482.21).
- In 2020, both models over-predicted GDP, but Random Forest (453.49) was slightly farther from the actual GDP (432.20) compared to OLS (446.75).
- In 2021, Random Forest again produced predictions (470.80) closer to actual GDP (440.83) than OLS (465.08).

In 2022, both models under-predicted GDP, with Random Forest (460.13) performing better than OLS (445.95).

CONCLUSION

This study examined the contribution of the fisheries subsector to Nigeria's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) using both Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression and Random Forest (RF) regression. The aim was to compare the explanatory and predictive power of traditional econometric and modern machine learning approaches. In relation to the research objectives, the study concludes that fisheries significantly and positively influence Nigeria's GDP. OLS provides interpretable results suitable for policy analysis, while Random Forest enhances predictive accuracy by capturing nonlinear patterns. Together, these models offer complementary insights, affirming that the fisheries subsector is not only vital for household livelihoods but also an important driver of macroeconomic growth in Nigeria.

REFERENCE

Adekoya, B. B., & Miller, J. W. (2004). *Fish production, poverty alleviation and food security in Nigeria*. Fisheries Society of Nigeria.

Allison, E. H., & Ellis, F. (2001). The livelihoods approach and management of small-scale fisheries. *Marine Policy*, 25(5), 377–388.

Ayanwale, A. O., Amusan, C. A., & Adejobi, A. O. (2017). Determinants of aquaculture investment in Nigeria. *International Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 2(4), 101–108.

Béné, C. (2006). Small-scale fisheries: Assessing their contribution to rural livelihoods in developing countries. *FAO Fisheries Circular No. 1008*. Food and Agriculture Organization.

Breiman, L. (2001). Random forests. *Machine Learning*, 45(1), 5–32.

Central Bank of Nigeria. (2021). *Statistical bulletin: Agriculture and environment statistics*.

Author.

Christiaensen, L., Demery, L., & Kuhl, J. (2011). The (evolving) role of agriculture in poverty reduction: An empirical perspective. *Journal of Development Economics*, 96(2), 239–254.

Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2018). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (5th ed.). SAGE.

Delgado, C. L., Wada, N., Rosegrant, M., Meijer, S., & Ahmed, M. (2003). *Fish to 2020: Supply and demand in changing global markets*. International Food Policy Research Institute (IFPRI) & WorldFish Center.

Diao, X., Hazell, P., & Thurlow, J. (2010). *The role of agriculture in African development*. International Food Policy Research Institute (IFPRI).

Eniola, O. V., Lawal, A. I., & Oyeleye, O. I. (2019). Fish production and economic growth in Nigeria: Empirical evidence from co-integration and causality model. *Journal of Applied Economics and Policy*, 12(2), 54–70.

Food and Agriculture Organization. (2020). *The state of world fisheries and aquaculture 2020: Sustainability in action*. FAO.

Gujarati, D. N., & Porter, D. C. (2009). *Basic econometrics* (5th ed.). McGraw-Hill.

James, G., Witten, D., Hastie, T., & Tibshirani, R. (2021). *An introduction to statistical learning: With applications in R* (2nd ed.). Springer.

Johnston, B. F., & Mellor, J. W. (1961). The role of agriculture in economic development. *American Economic Review*, 51(4), 566–593.

Mankiw, N. G. (2019). *Principles of economics* (9th ed.). Cengage Learning.

Mullainathan, S., & Spiess, J. (2017). Machine learning: An applied econometric approach. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 31(2), 87–106.

National Bureau of Statistics. (2021). *Nigerian gross domestic product report: Quarter four 2021*. NBS Publications.

Olaoye, O. J., Ashley-Dejo, S. S., Fakoya, E. O., Ikeweinwe, N. B., Alegbeleye, W. O., & Ashaolu, F. O. (2013). Assessment of socio-economic analysis of fish farming in Oyo State, Nigeria. *Global Journal of Science Frontier Research Agriculture and Veterinary Sciences*, 13(9), 45–59.

Oyinbo, O., & Abdulsalam, Z. (2015). Agricultural production and economic growth in Nigeria: Implication for rural poverty alleviation. *Quarterly Journal of Econometrics Research*, 1(1), 20–29.

Samuelson, P. A., & Nordhaus, W. D. (2010). *Economics* (19th ed.). McGraw-Hill.

Schultz, T. W. (1964). *Transforming traditional agriculture*. Yale University Press.

Stock, J. H., & Watson, M. W. (2020). *Introduction to econometrics* (4th ed.). Pearson.

Varian, H. R. (2014). Big data: New tricks for econometrics. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 28(2), 3–28.

Wooldridge, J. M. (2016). *Introductory econometrics: A modern approach* (6th ed.). Cengage Learning.

World Bank. (2020). *World development indicators 2020*. World Bank Publications.

Yusuf, S. A., & Salimonu, K. K. (2013). Agricultural output and economic growth in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 4(16), 14–26.

APPENDIX

Year	Fishery production(metric tons)	GDP(Billion)
1990	316328	54.04
1991	267705	59.53
1992	318415	52.06
1993	255499	56.72
1994	281232	80.4
1995	366101	140.92
1996	357484	185.73
1997	412220	200.85
1998	483482	218.42

1999	477365	59.15
2000	467095	69.17
2001	476544	73.56
2002	511719	95.05
2003	505839	104.74
2004	509201	135.76
2005	579537	175.67
2006	636901	238.45
2007	615507	278.26
2008	744575	339.48
2009	751006	295.01
2010	817516	366.99
2011	856614	414.47
2012	922652	463.97
2013	1000061	520.12
2014	1073059	574.18
2015	1027058	493.03
2016	1041498	404.65
2017	1212475	375.75
2018	1169478	421.74
2019	1114556	474.52
2020	1044812	432.2

2021	1080855	440.83
2022	1043230	477.4

GDP vs fishery

QQ-plot of standardized residuals

Jarque Bera Test

data: resid(model1)

X-squared = 0.9638, df = 2, p-value = 0.6176

studentized Breusch-Pagan test

data: modell

BP = 3.0902, df = 1, p-value = 0.07877

Durbin-Watson test

data: modell

DW = 0.60575, p-value = 3.476e-07

Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)

(Intercept) -8.450e+01 2.833e+01 -2.982 0.00553 **

fishery 5.085e-04 3.759e-05 13.525 1.52e-14 ***

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Residual standard error: 65.96 on 31 degrees of freedom

Multiple R-squared: 0.8551, Adjusted R-squared: 0.8504

F-statistic: 182.9 on 1 and 31 DF, p-value: 1.519e-14

```
randomForest(formula = GDP ~ fishery, data = mydata, ntree = 500, mtry = 1, importance =  
TRUE)
```

Type of random forest: regression

Number of trees: 500

No. of variables tried at each split: 1

Mean of squared residuals: 3020.322

% Var explained: 89.29